

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(+)-(R,2E,4Z)-7-(4'-(dimethylamino)phenyl)-4,6-dimethyl-7-oxohepta-2,4-dienoic acid	19.61	C17 H21 N O3	287.15180	1.80e9

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12912, RT=19.627 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 288.1590@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(+)-grenadamide	22.77	C ₂₁ H ₃₃ N O	315.25584	5.14e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15075, RT=22.763 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 316.3206@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(+/-)-6-Hydroxy-3-oxo-alpha-ionone	10.94	C13 H18 O3	222.12528	1.53e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #7076, RT=10.931 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 223.1325@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(-)-Caryophyllene oxide	19.14	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	220.18236	3.13e8

Piper retrofractum Rosita (F2) #12583, RT=19.150 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 221.1896@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(-)-cereolactam	13.59	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N O ₄	299.11531	1.67e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #8875, RT=13.613 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 300.1227@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(-)-Salsoline	11.90	C11 H15 N O2	193.10992	3.71e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #7722, RT=11.905 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 194.1173@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(1S,3R,7S,8S,8aR)-3,7-dimethyl-8-(2- {(4R,6R)-4-[2-(methylamino)-2- oxoethyl]-3-[4- (methylcarbamoyl)benzyl]-2-oxo-1,3- oxazinan-6-yl}ethyl)-1,2,3,7,8,8a- hexahydronaphthalen-1-yl (2S)-2- methylbutanoate	22.07	C35 H49 N3 O6	607.36272	6.15e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14584, RT=22.028 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 608.3702@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(2E)-octenoylcarnitine	18.14	C15 H27 N O4	285.19371	2.88e6

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(2E,4E)-2-methyl-hexa-2,4-dienoic acid (2'R,3'S)-allo-isooleucinol amide	21.23	C13 H23 N O2	225.17243	4.83e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14007, RT=21.205 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 226.1797@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(2E,4E)-N-(1,3-dihydroxy-3-methylpentan-2-yl)-2-methylhexa-2,4-dienamide	16.06	C13 H23 N O3	241.16746	2.98e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10520, RT=16.067 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 242.1748@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(2R)-2,3-Dihydroxypropyl 6-O-α-D-galactopyranosyl-β-D-galactopyranoside	1.96	C ₁₅ H ₂₈ O ₁₃	416.15224	1.79e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1269, RT=1.973 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 417.1595@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(2R,3R,4S)-4-(1,3-benzodioxol-5-yl)-1-{2-[(2,6-diethylphenyl)amino]-2-oxoethyl}-2-(4-propoxyphenyl)pyrrolidine-3-carboxylic acid	21.87	C33 H38 N2 O6	558.27214	4.04e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14491, RT=21.890 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 559.2794@(30;50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(2S,4S)-Pinnatanine	11.80	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₅	244.10547	9.47e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #7654, RT=11.801 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 245.1128@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(2S,5S)-5-(Hydroxymethyl)-2-isopropyl-1-methyl-9-octyl-1,2,4,5,6,8-hexahydro-3H-[1,4]diazonino[7,6,5-cd]indol-3-one	18.87	C ₂₅ H ₃₉ N ₃ O ₂	413.30373	7.04e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12400, RT=18.880 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 414.3109@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(2Z)-3-[(2S,4R)-2-(1,3-Benzodioxol-5-yl)-4-[(5E)-6-(1,3-benzodioxol-5-yl)-5-hexen-1-yl]-3-(1-piperidinylcarbonyl)cyclobutyl]-1-(1-piperidinyl)-2-propen-1-one	22.09	C38 H46 N2 O6	626.33464	4.33e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14623, RT=22.089 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 627.3419@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(2Z,4E)-5- [(1S,3S,11aR,12S,13S,15aS,15bS)- 3,13-Dihydroxy-1-isopropenyl- 4,4,6,6,12,15a,15b-heptamethyl-2-oxo- 1,2,3,3a,6,9,9a,10,11,11a,12,13,14,15, 15a,15b-hexadecahydro-4H-benzo[6, 7]indeno[1,2-b]pyrano [3',4':4,5]cyclopenta[1,2-f]pyrrolo[3,2,1- hi]indol-12-yl]-2-methoxy-N-(2-methyl- 2-propanyl)-2,4-pentadienamide	22.17	C ₄₇ H ₆₂ N ₂ O ₆	750.45934	2.18e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14681, RT=22.173 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C₄₇H₆₂N₂O₆ as [M+H]⁺

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
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Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14680, RT=22.171 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 751.4667@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(3a <i>S</i> ,6a <i>R</i>)-4-(3-Methoxyphenyl)-5-[(4 <i>E</i>)-4-octen-4-yl]- <i>N</i> -phenyl-2,3,6,6a-tetrahydro-3a(1 <i>H</i>)-pentalenamine	21.88	C ₂₉ H ₃₇ N O	415.28691	8.54e6

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(3R)-beta-Leucine	5.26	C6 H13 N O2	131.09437	1.61e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #3379, RT=5.262 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 132.1017@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(3R,4R,5S)-4,5-Dihydroxy-3-piperidinyl β-D-xylopyranoside	1.99	C10 H19 N O7	265.11568	4.22e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1290, RT=2.007 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 266.1230@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(3α,5α,8ξ,9ξ,14ξ,17β)-3,17-Diacetoxy-2,16-bis[1-(2-propyn-1-yl)-1-piperidiniumyl]androstande	22.30	C39 H60 N2 O4	620.45445	1.72e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14762, RT=22.298 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 621.4618@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(3β)-3-Acetoxyup-20(29)-en-28-yl 2-methyl-1H-imidazole-1-carboxylate	22.28	C37 H56 N2 O4	592.42320	1.60e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14745, RT=22.272 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 593.4305@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(3β)-3-Hydroxy-N-{2-[(2-hydroxybenzoyl)amino]ethyl}lup-20(29)-en-28-amide	22.18	C ₃₉ H ₅₈ N ₂ O ₄	618.43878	4.37e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14678, RT=22.169 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 619.4460@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(4aS,6R,8aS)-3-Methoxy-11-{12-[4-(1-piperidinylmethyl)phenoxy]dodecyl}-5,6,9,10,11,12-hexahydro-4aH-[1]benzofuro[3a,3,2-ef][2]benzazepin-6-ol	22.68	C40 H58 N2 O4	630.43889	8.05e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15010, RT=22.664 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 631.4462@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(4a <i>S</i> ,9 <i>R</i> ,15a <i>R</i>)-9-Hydroxy-7-[2-(4-methoxyphenyl)ethyl]-10,10-dimethyl-2-[4-(methylsulfonyl)benzyl]tetradecahydropyrido[4,3- <i>i</i>][1,6]oxazacyclotridecin-6(7 <i>H</i>)-one	21.77	C ₃₃ H ₄₈ N ₂ O ₆ S	600.32119	3.37e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14476, RT=21.867 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 601.2534@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(4E)-4-([4-(Benzyloxy)-2-methylphenyl](hydroxy)methylene)-5-(4-ethoxyphenyl)-1-[3-(4-morpholinyl)propyl]-2,3-pyrrolidinedione	21.62	C ₃₄ H ₃₈ N ₂ O ₆	570.27226	1.67e10

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14268, RT=21.579 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 571.2791@(30;50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(4R)-albaflavenol	17.19	C ₁₅ H ₂₄ O	220.18241	1.16e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11295, RT=17.223 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 221.1896@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(6S)-Hydroxyhyoscyamine	19.65	C17 H23 N O4	305.16227	2.13e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12920, RT=19.638 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 306.1696@(30;50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(6S,8aS)-N-[(2S)-3-(1-carbamimidoylpiperidin-3-yl)-1-(1-methyl-1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)-1-oxopropan-2-yl]-4-oxo-2-(3-phenylpropanoyl)octahydropyrrolo[1,2-a]pyrazine-6-carboxamide	21.99	C ₃₄ H ₄₂ N ₈ O ₄	626.33458	1.33e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14563, RT=21.997 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 627.3420@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(E)-3-hydroxy-2,4-dimethylhept-4-enamide	8.66	C9 H17 N O2	171.12569	2.07e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #5740, RT=8.892 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 172.1118@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(E)-Non-2-en-4,6,8-triynoic acid	16.04	C ₉ H ₄ O ₂	144.02099	4.26e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10483, RT=16.013 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 144.9919@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(R)-3-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)lactate	9.84	C9 H10 O4	182.05763	1.18e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #6352, RT=9.825 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 183.0650@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(R)-Coclaurine	19.35	C17 H19 N O3	285.13603	7.38e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12733, RT=19.371 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 286.1433@(30;50:80), +1)

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File name: Piper retrofractum

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Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(R)-Norcoclaurine	20.86	C16 H17 N O3	271.12035	4.66e9

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13770, RT=20.868 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 272.1276@(30:50:80), +1)

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(R,S)-Norlaudanosoline	20.49	C16 H17 N O4	287.11546	2.72e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13498, RT=20.474 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 288.1227@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(RS)-α-(2-Chloro-N-2,6-xylylacetylamido)-γ-butyrolactone	20.76	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₃	281.08159	2.92e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13713, RT=20.785 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 282.2060@(30;50;80), +1)

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(S)-1-Pyrroline-5-carboxylate	2.14	C5 H7 N O2	113.04745	2.76e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1379, RT=2.142 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C5 H7 N O2 as [M+H]⁺1

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1366, RT=2.122 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 114.0547@ (30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(S)-autumnaline	21.09	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N O ₅	373.18833	1.90e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13916, RT=21.074 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 374.1956@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(S)-beta-Methylindolepyruvate	16.09	C12 H11 N O3	217.07364	8.22e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10535, RT=16.088 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C12 H11 N O3 as [M+H]⁺

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10546, RT=16.105 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 218.0809@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(S)-malyl alpha-D-glucosaminide	1.83	C10 H17 N O9	295.08981	6.38e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1180, RT=1.839 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 296.0972@(30:50:80), +1)

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(S,S)-t-bu-box	19.08	C17 H30 N2 O2	294.23036	2.32e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12532, RT=19.076 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 295.2377@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(Z)-N-(4-decenoyl)-L-homoserine lactone	17.86	C14 H23 N O3	253.16758	7.97e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11712, RT=17.850 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 254.1748@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(±)-Isoalternatine A	19.92	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N O ₃	247.12038	2.91e9

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13128, RT=19.937 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 248.1277@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	(-)-α-Cedrene	20.28	C ₁₅ H ₂₄	204.18753	5.27e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13324, RT=20.217 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 205.1413@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
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22.83 C₄₂H₆₆N₂O₂ 630.51140

8.90e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15119, RT=22.828 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C₄₂H₆₆N₂O₂ as [M+H]⁺

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15116, RT=22.825 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 631.5189@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1,3,5-Norcaratriene	9.52	C7 H6	90.04682	4.82e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #6153, RT=9.524 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 91.0233@ (30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1,3,7-Trimethyl-8-(4-methyl-piperazin-1-yl)-3,7-dihydro-purine-2,6-dione	14.10	C13 H20 N6 O2	292.16463	1.26e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #9203, RT=14.099 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C13 H20 N6 O2 as [M+H]⁺

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #9416, RT=14.419 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 293.1645@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1,3-Dinitrobenzene-13C6	2.78	[13]C6 H4 N2 O4	174.03758	1.40e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1750, RT=2.726 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 174.9911@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1,4-Piperazinediylbis{[4-(nonyloxy)phenyl]methanone}	21.97	C36 H54 N2 O4	578.40746	4.21e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14536, RT=21.956 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 579.4149@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1,4-Piperazinediylbis[6,7,12,15,15-pentamethyl-3,10-diazatetracyclo[10.2.1.0~2,11~.0~4,9~]pentadeca-2,4(9),5,7,10-pentaen-1-yl]methanone}	21.87	C42 H50 N6 O2	670.39745	1.21e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14481, RT=21.875 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 671.4047@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1,8-Bis(4-butoxyphenyl)-2,7-bis(1-piperidinylmethyl)-1,8-octanedione	22.97	C40 H60 N2 O4	632.45458	5.48e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15220, RT=22.978 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 633.4619@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1-(3-phenylpropanoyl)-4-piperidinecarboxylic acid	18.11	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N O ₃	261.13614	2.03e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11900, RT=18.132 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 262.1435@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1-(piperidinomethyl)-2-naphthol	21.67	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N O	241.14623	2.11e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14347, RT=21.688 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 242.1534@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1-[3-(3,4-Dimethylphenyl)adamantan-1-yl]methanamine	19.96	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ N	269.21388	1.04e6

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1-[3-(Cyclopropylmethyl)-3-(hydroxymethyl)-1-piperidiny]-2-(methylsulfonyl)ethanone	20.33	C ₁₃ H ₂₃ N O ₂ S	257.14483	6.38e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13382, RT=20.303 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 258.1520@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1-Aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate	2.81	C4 H7 N O2	101.04748	1.43e7

Piper retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1809, RT=2.818 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 102.0547@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1-Boc-3-(aminomethyl)piperidine	14.74	C11 H22 N2 O2	214.16794	6.07e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #9630, RT=14.740 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 215.1752@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1-Boc-3-Vinyl-piperidine	18.40	C ₁₂ H ₂₁ N O ₂	211.15696	6.67e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12078, RT=18.399 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 212.1642@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1-Boc-4-(1-pyrrolidinyl)-3,6-dihydro-2H-pyridine	14.10	C ₁₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂	252.18340	7.05e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #9210, RT=14.111 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 253.1907@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1-Deoxy-D-glucitol	2.03	C6 H14 O5	166.08377	1.27e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1305, RT=2.029 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 167.0336@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1-Ethyl-6,7-dimethoxyisoquinolin-3-ol	18.26	C13 H15 N O3	233.10490	1.67e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11988, RT=18.264 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 234.1122@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1-Hydroxy-N-(2-([2-(3-pentadecylphenoxy)butanoyl]amino)ethyl)-2-naphthamide	22.15	C38 H54 N2 O4	602.40740	2.71e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14662, RT=22.145 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 603.4147@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1-t-butyl-4-ethylbenzene	17.94	C12 H18	162.14067	2.59e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11967, RT=18.232 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 163.0464@(30:50:80), +2)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1-{1-(3,4-Dimethylphenyl)-5-(1H-indol-3-yl)-4-[4-(4-morpholinylmethyl)phenyl]-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl}ethanone	21.79	C31 H33 N5 O2	507.26119	1.09e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14414, RT=21.781 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 508.2685@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1-{4-[(4-Methyl-1-piperazinyl)carbonyl]phenyl}-3-(4-{4-(4-morpholinyl)-6-[(3S)-tetrahydro-3-furanyloxy]-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl}phenyl)urea	20.76	C30 H36 N8 O5	588.28032	2.22e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13686, RT=20.748 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 589.2878@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	11-(Methacryloylamino)undecanoic acid	21.19	C ₁₅ H ₂₇ N O ₃	269.19869	1.40e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14008, RT=21.206 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 270.2060@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	11-Methyl-2Z,5Z-dodecadienoic acid	15.99	C13 H22 O2	210.16162	2.39e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10456, RT=15.970 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 211.1690@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	11-O-Demethyl-17-O-deacetylvindoline	20.55	C22 H28 N2 O5	400.19920	1.29e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13557, RT=20.560 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 401.2066@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	11-oxo-undeca-5,8-dienoic acid	11.40	C11 H16 O3	196.10963	1.67e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #7398, RT=11.420 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 197.1169@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	13-hydroxy dechlorofontonamide	21.79	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ N O ₃	325.16723	1.06e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14416, RT=21.783 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 326.1746@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	13-tetradecen-2,4-diyne-1-ol	19.73	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O	204.15112	2.04e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13012, RT=19.769 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 205.0856@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	16-Methoxy-2_3-dihydro-3-hydroxytabersonine	20.47	C22 H28 N2 O4	384.20445	1.33e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13492, RT=20.465 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 385.2118@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1_8-Diazacyclotetradecane-2_9-dione	13.11	C12 H22 N2 O2	226.16781	5.49e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #8520, RT=13.088 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 227.1751@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1_8-Dihydroxy-3-methylnaphthalene	20.02	C11 H10 O2	174.06788	4.62e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13108, RT=19.907 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 175.0386@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	1H-Benzotriazol-1-ylphosphonic acid	17.19	C6 H6 N3 O3 P	199.01545	4.16e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11250, RT=17.160 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 200.5624@(30:50:80), +2)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2,10-dimethyl 4-hydroxy-6-oxo-4-undecen-7-yne	15.06	C13 H20 O2	208.14609	3.73e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #9858, RT=15.078 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 209.1534@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2,2,6,6-Tetramethyl-4-piperidinol	19.88	C9 H19 N O	157.14644	7.67e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13087, RT=19.878 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 158.1537@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2,2-dimethyl-5-amino-6-(2'E-ene-4'-hydroxybutyryl)-4-chromone	17.95	C15 H17 N O4	275.11535	4.26e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11792, RT=17.970 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 276.1227@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2,2'-[1,3-Cyclohexanediylbis(oxy)]bis(N,N-dicyclohexylacetamide)	21.84	C ₃₄ H ₅₈ N ₂ O ₄	558.43871	7.42e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14455, RT=21.839 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 559.2794@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2,3-Methylenedioxy pyrovalerone	21.37	C16 H21 N O3	275.15168	1.81e10

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14160, RT=21.422 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 276.1500@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2,4-Bis(1-azepanylmethyl)-1,5-bis(4-ethoxyphenyl)-1,5-pentanedione	21.99	C35 H50 N2 O4	562.37609	2.55e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14551, RT=21.980 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 563.3836@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2,4-heptadienal	10.22	C7 H10 O	110.07296	1.25e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #6616, RT=10.229 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 111.0802@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2,6-Di-tert-butyl-1,4-benzoquinone	19.27	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₂	220.14599	5.59e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12620, RT=19.204 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 221.1897@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2,6-DI-TERT-BUTYL-4-(DIMETHYLAMINOMETHYL)PHENOL	22.61	C ₁₇ H ₂₉ N O	263.22454	6.47e8

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2,6-Dicyclododecylpyrrolo[3,4-f]isoindole-1,3,5,7(2H,6H)-tetrone	22.61	C ₃₄ H ₄₈ N ₂ O ₄	548.36059	2.32e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14975, RT=22.611 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C₃₄ H₄₈ N₂ O₄ as [M+H]⁺

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14966, RT=22.599 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 549.3680@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2,6-N-tert-Butylpyridine	10.53	C13 H21 N	191.16712	1.10e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #6813, RT=10.530 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 192.1743@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2,7-Bis[2-(1-pyrrolidinyl)ethyl]-4,9-bis[[2-(1-pyrrolidinyl)ethyl]amino}benzo[Imn][3,8]phenanthroline-1,3,6,8(2H,7H)-tetrone	22.12	C38 H52 N8 O4	684.41304	2.31e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14641, RT=22.115 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 685.4202@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
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21.84 C₃₈H₅₈N₂O₅ 622.43407

2.43e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14453, RT=21.835 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C₃₈H₅₈N₂O₅ as [M+H]⁺

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14410, RT=21.774 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 623.3106@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2-(alpha-D-Galactosyl)-sn-glycerol3-phosphate	1.74	C9 H19 O11 P	334.06592	1.09e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1118, RT=1.743 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 335.0732@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2-(beta-D-Glucosyl)-sn-glycerol	1.98	C9 H18 O8	254.09963	1.74e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1270, RT=1.974 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 255.1070@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2-(Hexadecyloxy)pyridine	22.88	C ₂₁ H ₃₇ N O	319.28707	4.17e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15141, RT=22.861 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 320.2943@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2-[(2-{2-[3-(Hydroxymethyl)-3,4-dihydro-2(1H)-isoquinolinyl]-2-oxoethyl]-4-pentenyl)amino]-3-methoxy-1-phenylpropyl 2-benzyl-6-heptenoate	21.91	C41 H50 N2 O6	666.36583	1.05e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14508, RT=21.914 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 667.3730@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2-[(4-Tetradecylidencyclohexyl)oxy]ethyl 2-(trimethylammonio)ethyl phosphate	22.07	C ₂₇ H ₅₄ N O ₅ P	503.37300	4.52e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14614, RT=22.075 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 504.3805@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2-[5-(4-Aminophenyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl]-1-(1-pyrrolidinyl)ethanone	20.19	C13 H16 N6 O	272.13855	6.60e6

Piper retrofractum Rosita (F2) #13174, RT=20.000 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 273.1310@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2-[Bis(3-methylbutyl)amino]-2-(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-propanediol	15.31	C ₁₄ H ₃₁ N ₂ O ₃	261.22993	2.44e6

Piper retrofractum Rosita (F2) #9972, RT=15.246 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 262.1409@ (30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2-benzyl-6-hydroxy-2-azabicyclo[2.2.2]octan-3-one	16.77	C14 H17 N O2	231.12558	7.50e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10980, RT=16.756 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 232.1329@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2-Ethylhexyl nitrate	6.31	C8 H17 N O3	175.12054	2.78e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #4034, RT=6.275 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 176.1278@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2-Heptyl-4-hydroxyquinoline-N-oxide	20.42	C16 H21 N O2	259.15699	3.58e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13501, RT=20.479 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 260.1278@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2-Hydroxy-3-[[[(4S,7S)-5-hydroxy-2,8-dimethyl-7-((2S,3R)-3-methyl-1-[methyl(2-pyridinyl)amino]-1-oxo-2-pentanyl)carbamoyl]-4-nonyl]carbamoyl]-4-oxo-5-phenylpentanoic acid	22.22	C36 H52 N4 O8	668.38164	1.37e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14697, RT=22.198 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 669.3888@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2-Phenoxy-3,4-dihydro-2H-pyrido[2,3-e][1,3,2]oxazaphosphinine 2-oxide	14.07	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃ P	262.05143	5.05e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #9127, RT=13.987 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 263.1725@ (30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2-{2-[(6-methoxy-2-morpholinopyridin-3-yl)amino]-2-oxoethoxy}acetic acid	19.35	C14 H19 N3 O6	325.12844	1.98e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12711, RT=19.338 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 326.1358@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	25-Azacholesterol	22.83	C ₂₆ H ₄₅ N O	387.34931	1.53e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15117, RT=22.826 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 388.3205@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	25P-NBOMe	22.13	C ₂₁ H ₂₉ N O ₃	343.21432	1.35e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14636, RT=22.107 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 344.2216@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	2H-Naphtho(1,8-bc)furan-2-one	21.50	C ₁₁ H ₆ O ₂	170.03647	1.31e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14205, RT=21.484 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 171.0438@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3,17-Dihydroxy-4,5-epoxyandro-2-ene-2-carbonitrile	21.84	C ₂₀ H ₂₇ N O ₃	329.19856	1.76e9

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14466, RT=21.855 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 330.2059@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3,3,5-Trimethylcyclohexyl 1-piperidinylacetate	21.21	C16 H29 N O2	267.21932	1.80e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14019, RT=21.223 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 268.2266@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3,3'-(dodecylimino)bispropane-1,2-diol	21.62	C18 H39 N O4	333.28731	1.86e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14314, RT=21.641 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 334.2946@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3,4,10,11-tetramethoxy-7,8,12b,13-tetrahydro-5H-6-azatetraphene	19.74	C21 H25 N O4	355.17781	3.97e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12997, RT=19.749 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 356.1851@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3,4-dimethyl-5-carboxyethyl-2-furanacrylic acid	16.69	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₅	238.08393	1.13e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10946, RT=16.704 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 239.0912@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3,5,7-Trimethyl-2E,4E,6E,8E-decatetraene	17.57	C13 H20	176.15634	2.43e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11524, RT=17.561 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 177.0544@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3,5,7-Trimethyl-2E,4E,6E,8E-undecatetraene	18.01	C14 H22	190.17188	6.41e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12073, RT=18.391 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 191.0700@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3-(1H-Imidazol-4-yl)-2-oxopropyl phosphate	1.86	C6 H7 N2 O5 P	218.00985	6.11e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1203, RT=1.874 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 219.0471@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3-(2'-acetoxy-3'-oxo-4'-methylpentyl)-indole	21.40	C16 H19 N O3	273.13601	3.86e10

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14146, RT=21.401 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 274.2619@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3-(2'-hydroxy-3'-oxo-4'-methyl-pentyl)-indole	19.32	C14 H17 N O2	231.12556	1.41e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12703, RT=19.327 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 232.1328@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)propanehydrazide	18.46	C17 H28 N2 O2	292.21455	2.53e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12117, RT=18.456 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 293.1719@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3-[4-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-1-piperazinyl]-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-amine	14.06	C13 H18 N6 O	274.15456	4.49e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #9182, RT=14.068 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 275.1725@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3-carboxy-4-methyl-5-pentyl-2-furanpropanoic acid	19.44	C14 H20 O5	268.13074	3.67e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12779, RT=19.436 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C14 H20 O5 as [M+Na]⁺

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12782, RT=19.442 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 269.0781@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3-Chloro-1,1,1-trifluoro-2-iodopropane	1.70	C3 H3 Cl F3 I	257.89168	3.01e6

Piper retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1095, RT=1.707 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 258.8989@ (30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3-Chloro-6-methoxypyridazine	2.79	C5 H5 Cl N2 O	144.00957	1.32e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1784, RT=2.779 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 144.9918@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3-Hydroxyaminophenol	2.01	C6 H7 N O2	125.04741	4.67e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1340, RT=2.083 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 125.9859@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3-Hydroxypyridine	5.56	C5 H5 N O	95.03691	1.57e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #3575, RT=5.564 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C5 H5 N O as [M+H]⁺

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #3573, RT=5.562 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 96.0442@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3-Methylbenzophenone	11.98	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O	196.08850	1.31e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #7768, RT=11.971 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 197.0958@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3-Methyloxindole	17.55	C9 H9 N O	147.06824	1.05e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11512, RT=17.544 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 148.0755@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3-n-heptyl-3-hydroxy-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline-2,4-dione	18.91	C16 H21 N O3	275.15176	7.40e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12420, RT=18.911 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 276.1591@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3-{6-[4-(3-Methoxyphenyl)-1-piperazinyl][1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-b]pyridazin-3-yl}-1-(4-propyl-1-piperazinyl)-1-propanone	21.70	C ₂₆ H ₃₆ N ₈ O ₂	492.29805	6.11e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14348, RT=21.689 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 493.3052@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	3097-C2	17.20	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N O ₄	251.11540	2.75e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11264, RT=17.179 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 252.1227@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
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4-(4-Cyclopentyl-1-piperazinyl)-N-[3-(1H-imidazol-1-yl)propyl]-6-methoxy-7-[3-(1-pyrrolidinyl)propoxy]-2-quinazolinamine

21.91 C₃₁H₄₆N₈O₂ 562.37609

5.02e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14500, RT=21.901 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 563.3835@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	4-(Aminoethyl)-1-N-Boc-piperidine	13.80	C ₁₂ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂	228.18332	4.23e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #8914, RT=13.670 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 229.1407@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	4-(tert-butyl)phenyl 3,5-dimethylisoxazole-4-carboxylate	20.76	C16 H19 N O3	273.13615	7.15e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13680, RT=20.739 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 274.1435@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	4-[(6E)-3-Hydroxy-8,10-dimethyl-2-(methylamino)-6-dodecen-1-yl]phenol	22.33	C ₂₁ H ₃₅ N O ₂	333.26636	2.88e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14799, RT=22.352 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 334.2737@(30:50;80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	4-[(Dimethylamino)methyl]-2,6-diisopropylphenol	22.15	C ₁₅ H ₂₅ N O	235.19320	7.93e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14676, RT=22.167 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 236.2005@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	4-[2-(Dipropylamino)ethyl]benzene-1,2-diol	18.34	C ₁₄ H ₂₃ N O ₂	237.17254	1.28e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12039, RT=18.339 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 238.1798@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	4-[[bis(2-hydroxyethyl)amino]methyl]-2,6-ditert-butylphenol	20.92	C ₁₉ H ₃₃ N ₃ O ₃	323.24551	8.00e7

Piper retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13786, RT=20.888 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 324.2527@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	4-Acetamidobutanoic acid	1.89	C6 H11 N O3	145.07355	8.35e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1215, RT=1.892 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 146.0809@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	4-Ethyl-1-[2-methyl-3-[4-(2-methyl-2-propanyl)phenyl]propyl]piperidine	21.78	C ₂₁ H ₃₅ N	301.27632	2.37e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14434, RT=21.808 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 302.1382@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	4-Hydroxycinnamoylmethane	19.32	C10 H10 O2	162.06781	6.75e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12678, RT=19.291 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 163.0751@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	4-Hydroxypropranolol	16.79	C16 H21 N O3	275.15177	3.76e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11004, RT=16.792 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 276.1591@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	4-Methylumbelliferylacetate	19.67	C12 H10 O4	218.05763	1.62e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12930, RT=19.654 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 219.0648@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	4-pentynylbenzene	15.59	C11 H12	144.09367	5.23e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10210, RT=15.599 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 144.9919@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	5-Hydroxy-1_4-naphthoquinone	19.94	C10 H6 O3	174.03136	2.53e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13108, RT=19.907 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 175.0386@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	5-Nonyl-2-[4-(octyloxy)phenyl]pyrimidine	22.31	C27 H42 N2 O	410.32915	2.16e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14752, RT=22.282 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 411.3364@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	5-Valerolactone	9.28	C5 H8 O2	100.05226	6.84e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #5983, RT=9.267 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 100.5262@(30:50:80), +2)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	5aTHQ-8n	22.38	C17 H27 N	245.21401	3.32e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14805, RT=22.361 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 246.2212@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	6-[(dimethylamino)methylidene]-6,7,8,9-tetrahydro-5H-benzo[a]cyclohepten-5-one	21.05	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N O	215.13063	1.25e9

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13896, RT=21.047 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 216.1380@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	6-Chloropyridazin-3-ol	1.98	C4 H3 Cl N2 O	129.99398	1.85e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1249, RT=1.944 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 131.0013@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	6-O-Methylnorlaudanosoline	17.51	C17 H19 N O4	301.13107	2.18e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11478, RT=17.495 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 302.1382@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	7,13-Bis(4-methoxybenzyl)-1,4,10-trioxa-7,13-diazacyclopentadecane	21.78	C ₂₆ H ₃₈ N ₂ O ₅	458.27736	4.81e7

Piper retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14404, RT=21.766 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 459.2847@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	7-Hydroxy-1(3H)-isobenzofuranone	13.58	C8 H6 O3	150.03154	1.97e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #8862, RT=13.594 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 151.0388@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	7-O-Acetylsalutaridinol	21.28	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ N O ₅	371.17259	1.10e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14065, RT=21.289 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 372.1799@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	7-phenyl heptanoic acid	16.00	C13 H18 O2	206.13041	1.39e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10564, RT=16.132 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 207.1465@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	7_10_13_16-Docosatetraenoylethanolamine	22.42	C24 H41 N O2	375.31325	1.71e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14844, RT=22.420 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 376.3204@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	7_8-Didehydro-4_5-epoxy-3-methoxy-17-methoxy-(5_)-morphinan-6-one	13.61	C18 H19 N O3	297.13616	1.64e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #8873, RT=13.608 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C18 H19 N O3 as [M+H]⁺

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #8858, RT=13.587 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 298.1433@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	7H-[1,2,4]Triazolo[4,3-b][1,2,4]triazole-3,7-diamine	4.81	C3 H5 N7	139.06070	2.58e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #3081, RT=4.802 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 140.0679@ (30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	8-(4'-O-methyl-α-rhamnopyranosyloxy)-2-methylquinoline	13.94	C17 H21 N O5	319.14155	1.29e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #9090, RT=13.934 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 320.1488@ (30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	8-Formyl-1-naphthoic acid	21.51	C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₃	200.04697	3.08e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14233, RT=21.526 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 201.0542@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	8-[[[(4'-{4-[4-(Hydroxymethyl)phenyl]-6-[(1,3,3-trimethyl-6-azabicyclo[3.2.1]oct-6-yl)methyl]-1,3-dioxan-2-yl]-3-biphenyl)methyl]amino}-8-oxooctanoic acid	21.99	C43 H56 N2 O6	696.41271	3.16e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14556, RT=21.988 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 697.4202@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	9-amino-nonanoic acid	9.92	C ₉ H ₁₉ N O ₂	173.14131	3.36e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #6409, RT=9.914 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 174.1486@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	[7-(6-Oxo-1,6-dihydro-9H-purin-9-yl)heptyl]phosphonic acid	21.76	C ₁₂ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₄ P	314.11494	1.11e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14401, RT=21.763 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 315.1779@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Acetonecyanohydrin	4.80	C4 H7 N O	85.05262	2.46e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #3090, RT=4.817 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 86.0599@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Aflaquinolone E	17.86	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N O ₄	285.09975	4.91e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11727, RT=17.871 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 286.1435@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Aglepristone	22.38	C ₂₉ H ₃₇ N O ₂	431.28179	1.43e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14830, RT=22.397 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 432.2891@(30;50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Aleptic acid	19.47	C ₁₄ H ₂₄ O ₂	224.17735	3.38e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12801, RT=19.469 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 225.1846@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	alpha-Curcumene	19.61	C15 H22	202.17189	6.65e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12910, RT=19.622 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 203.0700@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Alprenolol	18.13	C ₁₅ H ₂₃ N O ₂	249.17253	1.15e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11893, RT=18.122 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 250.1798@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Amfepramone	19.81	C13 H19 N O	205.14641	6.23e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13044, RT=19.818 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 206.1536@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Amfepramone	19.96	C13 H19 N O	205.14632	6.59e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13155, RT=19.974 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 206.1536@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Amidenin	17.54	C ₁₀ H ₁₇ N O	167.13081	1.04e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11496, RT=17.522 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 168.1381@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Anandamide (18:3, n-6)	19.52	C ₂₀ H ₃₅ N O ₂	321.26631	4.64e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12826, RT=19.503 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 322.2736@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Anhydroecgonine methyl ester	14.46	C10 H15 N O2	181.11008	2.48e7

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Anti-13,15-dihydroxyretenellin B	19.03	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N O ₆	385.15206	6.89e6

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Arachidonoyl amide	21.87	C ₂₀ H ₃₃ N O	303.25575	3.65e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14473, RT=21.864 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 304.2631@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Arachidonoylamide	21.18	C ₂₀ H ₃₃ N O	303.25582	3.95e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14004, RT=21.202 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 304.2631@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Arachidonoylmorpholine	22.64	C ₂₄ H ₃₉ N O ₂	373.29743	1.18e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14932, RT=22.548 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 374.3412@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Arecoline	8.17	C8 H13 N O2	155.09441	7.79e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #5262, RT=8.162 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 156.1017@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Armochaetoglobin E	21.46	C33 H40 N2 O6	560.28783	3.20e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14181, RT=21.450 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 561.2948@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Asparagine	1.77	C4 H8 N2 O3	132.05324	4.05e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1137, RT=1.772 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 133.0606@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Aspernidine A	21.79	C ₂₄ H ₃₃ N O ₄	399.24034	2.29e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14437, RT=21.813 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 400.2476@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Asperophiobolin B	22.65	C ₂₅ H ₃₅ N O ₃	397.26104	2.63e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14996, RT=22.644 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 398.2684@(30;50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Atropine	19.14	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ N O ₃	289.16733	1.34e9

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12582, RT=19.149 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 290.1746@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Aurachin RE	22.44	C ₂₅ H ₃₃ N O ₃	395.24550	1.73e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14852, RT=22.430 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 396.2527@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	BE-14106	22.84	C ₂₇ H ₃₇ N O ₃	423.27677	3.18e7

Piper retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15129, RT=22.844 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 424.3625@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Be-52211	21.76	C23 H33 N O3	371.24553	3.10e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14403, RT=21.765 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 372.2528@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	BE-52211 B	22.09	C23 H33 N O2	355.25036	6.36e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14632, RT=22.101 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 356.2215@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Benserazide	2.00	C10 H15 N3 O5	257.10234	2.61e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1279, RT=1.990 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 258.1096@ (30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Benzaldehyde	13.49	C7 H6 O	106.04170	1.29e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #8784, RT=13.477 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 107.0490@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Benzene	12.09	C6 H6	78.04681	5.26e7

Piper retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #7850, RT=12.092 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 79.0541@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Benzyl (2E, 13α, 14β, 17α, 20S)-2-[2-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-2-oxoethylidene]-3-oxolanosta-8,24-dien-21-oate	22.82	C44 H62 N2 O4	682.47069	3.66e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15102, RT=22.804 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 683.5499@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Bhimamycin C	18.68	C17 H17 N O5	315.11019	1.82e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12260, RT=18.672 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 316.1174@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	BOC-LYS(FMOC)-OH	20.47	C ₂₆ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₆	468.22542	3.87e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13482, RT=20.452 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 469.2327@(30;50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Brasilamide E	18.58	C15 H19 N O2	245.14117	3.61e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12195, RT=18.574 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 246.1092@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	BRN 2646116	21.94	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N O	243.16167	1.83e6

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	butacaine	19.76	C18 H30 N2 O2	306.23035	2.62e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13002, RT=19.757 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 307.2376@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	C16 Sphinganine	21.79	C16 H35 N O2	273.26634	1.31e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14421, RT=21.790 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 274.1433@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Camylofin	21.06	C ₁₉ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₂	320.24592	3.25e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13894, RT=21.042 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 321.2531@(30;50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Caprolactam	7.58	C6 H11 N O	113.08389	4.05e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #4890, RT=7.592 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 114.0912@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Capsaicin	17.95	C ₁₈ H ₂₇ N O ₃	305.19881	1.10e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11811, RT=17.998 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 306.2787@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Carbazomadurin A	22.10	C22 H27 N O3	353.19850	7.07e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14647, RT=22.125 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 354.2058@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Carbazochinocin G	11.96	C17 H17 N O2	267.12547	1.57e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #7798, RT=12.014 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 268.2451@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	CARBOBENZYLOXYVALYLGLYCINE	16.25	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₅	308.13866	1.13e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10646, RT=16.255 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 309.1458@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Chaetoindicin C	19.56	C16 H19 N O4	289.13095	1.33e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12766, RT=19.418 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 290.1747@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Chartarutine B	22.31	C ₂₃ H ₃₁ N O ₃	369.22989	1.70e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14755, RT=22.288 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 370.2370@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	CHEMBRDG-BB 5535613	20.18	C17 H29 N O2	279.21956	8.49e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13374, RT=20.292 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 280.1338@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Choline	1.98	C5 H13 N O	103.09947	1.82e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1286, RT=2.000 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 104.1068@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	cis-Jasmone	15.06	C11 H16 O	164.11992	2.35e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #9867, RT=15.090 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 165.0544@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Clonoamide	20.48	C ₁₅ H ₂₅ N O ₂	251.18824	3.35e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13488, RT=20.461 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 252.1956@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Cordylactam	18.06	C13 H15 N O4	249.09980	4.86e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11893, RT=18.122 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 250.1798@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	coronatine	17.44	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ N O ₄	319.17776	9.49e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11410, RT=17.391 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 320.2579@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Cyclo-(L-Ile-L-Leu-L-Leu-L-Leu-L-Leu)	10.49	C30 H55 N5 O5	565.41950	6.38e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #6798, RT=10.508 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 566.4267@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

14-Jul-2025 11:23

File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	D-Cathinone	10.81	C9 H11 N O	149.08381	3.49e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #7004, RT=10.821 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 150.0911@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	D-Pipecolicacid	4.80	C6 H11 N O2	129.07875	5.10e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #3062, RT=4.772 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 130.0860@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Dauricine	21.95	C38 H44 N2 O6	624.31890	8.30e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14528, RT=21.945 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 625.3264@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Deacetyldemethylanisomycin	11.87	C11 H15 N O3	209.10484	1.58e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #7694, RT=11.862 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 210.1121@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	demethylsuberosin	20.26	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₃	230.09403	1.51e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13360, RT=20.271 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 231.1013@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Dendryphielic acid B	9.91	C ₉ H ₁₄ O ₃	170.09403	5.34e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #6478, RT=10.017 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 171.1489@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Deoxyneo-beta-hydroxyaspergillid acid	12.94	C ₁₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	224.15215	2.53e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #8430, RT=12.954 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 225.1595@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Diamantane	16.18	C14 H20	188.15631	7.30e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10616, RT=16.211 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 189.0466@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Dianisylamine	19.35	C16 H19 N O2	257.14116	1.04e9

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12702, RT=19.326 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 258.1485@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
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Dibenzyloxy 2,2'-[[[(2S,3R,4R,5S)-3,4-dihydroxy-1,6-diphenyl-2,5-hexanediyloxy]diimino]bis(3-methylbutanoate)]

22.44

C₄₂H₅₂N₂O₆

680.38158

1.68e7

Piper retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14871, RT=22.459 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 681.3889@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Dibutylone	6.44	C13 H17 N O3	235.12041	3.47e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #4128, RT=6.420 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 236.1277@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Dichotomocej B	19.91	C ₁₄ H ₂₅ N O ₂	239.18818	2.62e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13098, RT=19.894 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 240.1954@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	dicyclohexylcarbodiimide	11.69	C13 H22 N2	206.17792	1.71e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #7575, RT=11.684 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 207.1853@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Diethanolamine	1.80	C4 H11 N O2	105.07876	7.24e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1153, RT=1.798 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 106.0860@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Diethyl {[5-(propoxymethyl)-2-furyl]methyl}phosphonate	16.16	C13 H23 O5 P	290.12807	7.27e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10762, RT=16.428 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 291.1563@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Diethyl {phenyl[(3,4,5-trimethoxybenzoyl)amino]methyl} phosphonate	16.61	C ₂₁ H ₂₈ N O ₇ P	437.15966	2.77e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10866, RT=16.584 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 438.1671@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Dihydroevocarpine	22.82	C ₂₃ H ₃₅ N O	341.27140	3.06e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15110, RT=22.815 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 342.2059@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Dimethocaine	17.07	C ₁₆ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂	278.19903	2.48e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11199, RT=17.085 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 279.2064@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Dimethyl 1-(4-methoxybenzyl)-6-oxo-1,4,5,6-tetrahydro-2,3-pyridinedicarboxylate	17.00	C17 H19 N O6	333.12075	3.90e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11142, RT=17.000 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 334.1281@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	DTPA anhydride	15.06	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₈	357.11827	1.58e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #9834, RT=15.041 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 358.1257@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Ecgonine	8.76	C9 H15 N O3	185.10495	4.38e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #5657, RT=8.765 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C9 H15 N O3 as [M+H]⁺1

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #5647, RT=8.752 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 186.1122@ (30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Epinephrine(OrL-Adrenaline)	9.23	C9 H13 N O3	183.08928	1.45e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #5946, RT=9.211 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 184.0966@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Erinacerin D	19.45	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N O ₆	375.16786	5.17e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12778, RT=19.435 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 376.2114@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Ethyl 5,6-dimethoxy-3-({[4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3-methyl-1-piperazinyl]acetyl}amino)-1H-indole-2-carboxylate	19.32	C ₂₇ H ₃₄ N ₄ O ₆	510.24865	1.32e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12710, RT=19.336 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 511.2560@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	fencamfamin	17.91	C15 H21 N	215.16706	1.80e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11749, RT=17.905 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 216.1744@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Ficine	20.45	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N O ₄	337.13097	1.83e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13487, RT=20.457 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C₂₀H₁₉N O₄ as [M+H]⁺1

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13485, RT=20.455 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 338.1383@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	FR-900130	8.17	C4 H5 N O2	99.03182	5.44e6

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Frustulosin	19.61	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₃	202.06270	1.71e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12910, RT=19.622 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 203.0700@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Fuligopyrone	21.30	C18 H17 N O5	327.11015	3.65e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14091, RT=21.324 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 328.1174@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Furfurylamine	2.01	C5 H7 N O	97.05253	3.25e7

Piper retrofractum Rosita (F2) #1088, RT=1.696 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 98.0235@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Fusaricate I	16.96	C ₁₄ H ₂₁ N O ₃	251.15181	6.53e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11128, RT=16.978 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 252.1591@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Fyrol DMMP	4.97	C3 H9 O3 P	124.02872	4.27e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #3191, RT=4.972 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C3 H9 O3 P as [M+H]⁺

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #3205, RT=4.995 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 125.0360@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Ggamma-L-Glutamyl-L-glutamicacid	1.83	C10 H16 N2 O7	276.09525	5.51e6

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Glaciapyrrole B	21.83	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ N O ₃	317.19989	1.81e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14428, RT=21.799 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 318.2787@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Glycerophosphoglycerol	1.82	C6 H15 O8 P	246.04997	4.66e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1166, RT=1.818 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 247.0573@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Guaiazulene	20.56	C15 H18	198.14062	7.64e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13575, RT=20.587 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 199.1327@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Hexanoylglycine	7.78	C8 H15 N O3	173.10499	4.57e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #5005, RT=7.768 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 174.1122@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Homoanatoxin A	19.03	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ N O	179.13083	1.00e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12498, RT=19.029 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 180.1382@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Ilanepyrrolal	18.22	C14 H15 N O3	245.10481	4.99e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11964, RT=18.228 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 246.1121@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Indole-3-ethanol	11.90	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N O	161.08380	2.44e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #7711, RT=11.888 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 162.0911@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Indosespene	22.15	C23 H29 N O3	367.21426	1.16e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14652, RT=22.133 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 368.2214@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Iromycin A	21.83	C ₁₉ H ₂₉ N O ₂	303.21916	3.74e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14473, RT=21.864 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 304.2631@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	iso-Debromo-laurinterol	19.27	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O	216.15112	3.19e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12665, RT=19.270 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C₁₅H₂₀O as [M+H]⁺

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12650, RT=19.249 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 217.1584@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Isoprenaline	11.09	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ N O ₃	211.12051	1.99e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #7188, RT=11.102 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 212.1278@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	itriglumide	21.65	C33 H38 N2 O4	526.28227	4.75e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14332, RT=21.666 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 527.2896@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Jiangrine A	18.62	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N O ₅	305.12584	5.85e6

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Kobutimycin B	18.52	C ₂₀ H ₂₇ N O ₅	361.18836	1.50e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12148, RT=18.503 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 362.1957@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	L-2-Amino-4-chloropent-4-enoate	3.98	C5 H8 Cl N O2	149.02408	1.70e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #2558, RT=3.991 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 150.0314@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Laurdan	22.94	C ₂₄ H ₃₅ N O	353.27132	2.24e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15187, RT=22.929 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 354.2786@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Lidocaine N-oxide	14.77	C ₁₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	250.16784	1.06e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #9642, RT=14.757 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 251.1752@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	ligurobustoside M	17.16	C ₂₆ H ₄₀ O ₁₅	592.23887	3.62e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11265, RT=17.180 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 593.2462@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Louisianin B	10.62	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N O ₂	191.09441	5.36e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #6870, RT=10.618 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 192.1016@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	m-dPEG(R)4-amine	2.16	C9 H21 N O4	207.14667	1.20e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1406, RT=2.185 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 208.1539@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Maniwamycin B	18.56	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	200.15221	5.89e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12120, RT=18.462 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 201.1635@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	MDPBP	19.89	C15 H19 N O3	261.13604	4.33e8

Piper retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13086, RT=19.877 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 262.1433@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Menadione	19.73	C11 H8 O2	172.05221	5.51e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12996, RT=19.749 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 173.0594@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Meptazinol	21.70	C ₁₅ H ₂₃ N O	233.17757	2.98e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14362, RT=21.708 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 234.1848@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Mesitylethylene	20.86	C11 H14	146.10929	5.01e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13759, RT=20.851 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 147.1166@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Methanandamide	22.70	C23 H39 N O2	361.29759	5.04e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15022, RT=22.681 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 362.3048@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Methyl 7-oxo-11E-tetradecenoate	16.84	C15 H26 O3	254.18756	2.29e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11019, RT=16.813 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 255.0988@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Methyl N-(9-((3β)-3-hydroxy-28-oxolup-20(29)-en-28-yl]amino)nonanoyl)-L-phenylalaninate	22.43	C ₄₉ H ₇₆ N ₂ O ₅	772.57414	5.77e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14866, RT=22.450 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 773.5814@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Methyl N-[(4S,5S)-5-({N-[(benzyloxy)carbonyl]-L-alanyl}amino)-4-hydroxy-6-phenylhexanoyl]-L-valyl-L-valinate	21.97	C ₃₄ H ₄₈ N ₄ O ₈	640.35021	5.85e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14554, RT=21.983 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 641.3577@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Methyl {(2S)-1-[(2S)-2-{5-[6-(3-ethylphenyl)-10-{2-[(2S)-1-(2S)-2-[(methoxycarbonyl)amino]-3-methylbutanoyl]-2-pyrrolidinyl]-1H-imidazol-5-yl}indolo[1,2-c][1,3]benzoxazin-3-yl]-1H-imidazol-2-yl}-1-pyrrolidinyl]-3-methyl-1-oxo-2-butanyl}carbamate	21.94	C51 H59 N9 O7	909.45458	2.94e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14541, RT=21.964 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 910.4617@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Methylphenidate	21.71	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ N O ₂	233.14121	1.54e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14362, RT=21.708 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 234.1848@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Metoprolol	19.37	C ₁₅ H ₂₅ N O ₃	267.18309	1.18e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12754, RT=19.400 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 268.1904@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Microansamycin C	21.09	C17 H19 N O5	317.12585	8.73e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13915, RT=21.073 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 318.1331@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Microansamycin H	14.39	C17 H21 N O6	335.13644	9.60e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #9367, RT=14.345 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 336.1201@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	mociprazine	18.30	C22 H32 N2 O3	372.24071	7.68e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12019, RT=18.311 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 373.2481@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Molindone	17.07	C16 H24 N2 O2	276.18350	8.92e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11191, RT=17.074 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 277.1908@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Monasnicotinate A	21.72	C21 H27 N O4	357.19344	5.66e7

Piper retrofractum Rosita (F2) #14361, RT=21.707 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 358.2007@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Monaspyranoindole	18.85	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N O	201.11509	4.19e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12390, RT=18.866 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 202.1224@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Mortivinacin C	9.61	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ N O ₅	281.12599	9.95e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #6213, RT=9.615 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 282.1332@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Myrtecaïne	22.39	C ₁₇ H ₃₁ N O	265.24016	2.45e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14840, RT=22.413 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 266.2475@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N,N-Dibutylethanolamine	6.98	C ₁₀ H ₂₃ N O	173.17772	1.05e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #4479, RT=6.961 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 174.1850@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N,N-diethyl-3-hydroxybut-2-enamide	7.68	C8 H15 N O2	157.11003	2.02e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #4954, RT=7.688 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 158.0962@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N,N-Diethyl-6-(mesityloxy)-1-hexanamine	22.97	C ₁₉ H ₃₃ N O	291.25585	3.80e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15204, RT=22.955 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 292.2631@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N,N-DIETHYLNIPECOTAMIDE	16.09	C10 H20 N2 O	184.15736	8.10e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10536, RT=16.092 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 185.1646@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N,N-Diisopropylethylamine (DIPEA)	6.45	C8 H19 N	129.15148	1.13e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #4150, RT=6.452 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 130.1588@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N,N'-1,2-Ethanediylobis(3-cyclopentylpropanamide)	20.31	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₂	308.24600	1.23e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13394, RT=20.321 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 309.2533@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N,N'-Bis[4-(heptyloxy)phenyl]nonanediamide	21.95	C ₃₅ H ₅₄ N ₂ O ₄	566.40740	2.56e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14524, RT=21.938 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 567.4139@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N,N'-Bis(4-[2,4-bis(2-methylbutan-2-yl)phenoxy]butyl)terephthalamide	22.48	C ₄₈ H ₇₂ N ₂ O ₄	740.54778	7.10e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14890, RT=22.486 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 741.5554@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N,N'-Bis(4-(N,N'-diethyl-N-(ethylcarbamoyl)carbamimidoyl)phenyl)terephthalamide	22.32	C ₃₆ H ₄₆ N ₈ O ₄	654.36619	1.84e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14769, RT=22.308 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 655.3732@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-(2,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)-11-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-10-methyl-8-phenyl-8,11-dihydropyrazolo[3',4':4,5]pyrimido[1,2-a]quinoxalin-6-amine	21.87	C35 H32 N6 O4	600.24626	2.13e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14477, RT=21.868 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C35 H32 N6 O4 as [M+H]⁺

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14476, RT=21.867 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 601.2534@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-(2-methyl-3-oxodecanoyl)pyrrolidine	19.81	C15 H27 N O2	253.20383	2.77e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13035, RT=19.803 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 254.2111@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-(2E,9Z-hexadecadienoyl)-homoserine lactone	22.28	C ₂₀ H ₃₃ N O ₃	335.24556	1.59e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14763, RT=22.299 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 336.2528@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-(3,4-Dimethoxybenzyl)-2-[2-ethyl-4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2-methyltetrahydro-2H-pyran-4-yl]ethanamine	21.72	C ₂₆ H ₃₇ N O ₄	427.27159	2.88e7

Piper retrofractum Rosita (F2) #14386, RT=21.741 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 428.2789@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-(4-phenyl-3-oxo-tetranoyl)-homoserine lactone	19.14	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N O ₄	261.09983	1.74e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12586, RT=19.153 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 262.1071@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-(4-tert-Butylbenzyl)-3-(morpholin-4-yl)propan-1-amine	18.48	C ₁₈ H ₃₀ N ₂ O	290.23534	1.80e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12123, RT=18.465 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 291.1563@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-(7-methyloctanoyl)homoserine lactone	11.42	C13 H23 N O3	241.16734	2.01e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #7338, RT=11.330 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 242.1535@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-(Chloroacetyl)norleucine	7.42	C8 H14 Cl N O3	207.06592	5.97e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #4864, RT=7.551 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 208.0941@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-(Indol-3-ylethyl)-2-hydroxy-3-methylpe	17.39	C16 H22 N2 O2	274.16771	1.60e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11553, RT=17.606 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 275.1614@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-[(Z)-hexadec-9-enoyl]glycine methyl ester (Z9-C16:1-NAGME)	21.29	C19 H35 N O3	325.26113	1.37e8

Piper retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14038, RT=21.249 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 326.2684@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
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N-[1-(1H-Benzimidazol-2-yl)-5-carbamimidamido-1-oxo-2-pentanyl]-2-(2,6-dimethyltyrosyl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-3-isoquinolinecarboxamide

21.89

C₃₄ H₄₀ N₈ O₄

624.31902

4.20e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14492, RT=21.890 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 625.3262@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-[2-(Benzylamino)-2-oxo-1-(4-pyridinyl)ethyl]-2-[5-(5-methyl-2-furyl)-2H-tetrazol-2-yl]-N-[3-(4-morpholinyl)propyl]acetamide	21.79	C ₂₉ H ₃₄ N ₈ O ₄	558.27202	1.62e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14420, RT=21.789 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 559.2794@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
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N-[4-(4-Amino-1-{2-[4-(dimethylamino)-1-piperidinyl]ethyl}-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-d]pyrimidin-3-yl)-2-methoxyphenyl]-3,3-dimethylbutanamide

22.09

C27 H40 N8 O2

508.32930

1.47e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14626, RT=22.092 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 509.3366@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-Acetyl-L-tyrosine	16.54	C11 H13 N O4	223.08412	2.15e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10854, RT=16.567 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 224.1643@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-arachidonoyl dihydroxypropylamine	22.56	C23 H39 N O3	377.29256	4.21e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14946, RT=22.570 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 378.3361@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-arachidonoyl glycine	21.83	C22 H35 N O3	361.26123	2.61e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14509, RT=21.916 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 362.1721@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-Benzoyl-L-leucine methyl ester	16.37	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ N O ₃	249.13621	1.21e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10734, RT=16.388 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 250.1435@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-Benzyl-6-(4-phenylbutoxy)-1-hexanamine	22.07	C ₂₃ H ₃₃ N O	339.25563	5.90e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14608, RT=22.066 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 340.1902@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-Butylscopolamine	19.26	C ₂₁ H ₂₉ N O ₄	359.20922	3.05e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12672, RT=19.282 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 360.2164@ (30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-Butyryl-L-homoserinelactone	9.42	C8 H13 N O3	171.08931	8.38e7

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-Cyclohexyl-1-[[3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)propanoyl](2-furylmethyl)amino]cyclohexanecarboxamide	22.07	C35 H52 N2 O4	564.39171	2.15e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14599, RT=22.054 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 565.3993@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-decanoyl-homoserine lactone	21.26	C ₁₄ H ₂₅ N O ₃	255.18310	2.26e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14052, RT=21.271 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 256.1904@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-demethylphiosetin	19.49	C ₂₁ H ₂₉ N O ₅	375.20408	1.02e9

Piper retrofractum Rosita (F2) #12810, RT=19.483 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 376.2115@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-ethyl arachidonoyl amine	22.81	C22 H37 N O	331.28715	1.38e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15108, RT=22.813 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 332.2945@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-Ethylretinamide	21.88	C22 H33 N O	327.25575	1.08e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14468, RT=21.857 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 328.1902@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-Feruloyltyramine	14.31	C18 H19 N O4	313.13104	4.32e7

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-lauroyl glycine	17.91	C14 H27 N O3	257.19873	1.25e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11742, RT=17.895 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 258.2061@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone	5.26	C5 H9 N O	99.06820	5.23e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #3376, RT=5.257 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 100.5262@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-Methylcaprolactam	8.74	C7 H13 N O	127.09955	1.62e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #5646, RT=8.751 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 128.1068@ (30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-oleoyl proline	22.65	C ₂₃ H ₄₁ N O ₃	379.30804	1.33e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15015, RT=22.671 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 380.3153@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-tetradecanoyl-homoserine lactone	20.28	C18 H33 N O3	311.24571	8.85e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13380, RT=20.302 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 312.2530@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-{11-[(7beta,8xi,9beta,13alpha,14beta,17alpha)-3,17-Dihydroxyestra-1(10),2,4-trien-7-yl]undecyl}-Nalpha-hexanoyl-L-phenylalaninamide	22.66	C44 H66 N2 O4	686.50109	4.46e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15027, RT=22.689 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 687.5083@(30;50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
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21.79 C37 H44 N2 O6 612.31896

1.11e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14408, RT=21.773 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 613.3264@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N-[[4-(Cyclohexylsulfamoyl)phenyl]carbamothioyl]acetamide	17.97	C15 H21 N3 O3 S2	355.10268	2.72e6

Piper retrofractum Rosita (F2) #12045, RT=18.348 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 356.1851@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N1-[4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl]-2-phenylbutanamide	21.63	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ F ₃ N O	307.11788	6.53e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14319, RT=21.648 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 308.1252@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N1-acetyl-N7-4''-methyl-3''-pentenoyl cadaverine	13.94	C13 H24 N2 O2	240.18344	1.28e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #9078, RT=13.916 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 241.1907@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N5-(L-1-Carboxyethyl)-L-ornithine	6.14	C8 H16 N2 O4	204.11052	1.87e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #3937, RT=6.125 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 205.0240@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Nalpha-Benzoyl-N-[(2S)-1-hydroxy-3-phenyl-2-propanyl]-L-phenylalaninamide	21.17	C25 H26 N2 O3	402.19377	1.02e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13992, RT=21.185 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 403.2011@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Neovasipyrindone D	22.22	C ₂₄ H ₃₃ N O ₃	383.24560	2.50e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14700, RT=22.205 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 384.2528@(30;50;80), +1)

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Nigerypyrone C	20.85	C13 H14 O4	234.08881	5.83e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13774, RT=20.871 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 235.1689@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Nitrilotri-2,1-ethanediyl tricarbamate	6.70	C ₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆	278.12380	1.87e6

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Nitromethanetriol	1.59	C ₃ H ₃ N ₁ O ₅	109.00119	3.68e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1013, RT=1.583 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C₃H₃N₁O₅ as [M+H]⁺

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1005, RT=1.572 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 110.0291@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Nonadecyl 1H-pyrrole-1-carboxylate	22.57	C ₂₄ H ₄₃ N O ₂	377.32884	2.63e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14945, RT=22.566 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C₂₄ H₄₃ N O₂ as [M+H]⁺1

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14946, RT=22.570 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 378.3361@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	nor-6α-Oxycodol	19.68	C17 H21 N O4	303.14671	1.67e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12946, RT=19.675 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 304.1539@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Normorphine	21.18	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N O ₃	271.12047	2.68e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13986, RT=21.177 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 272.1277@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	NP-000510	21.89	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ N O ₃	339.18283	8.83e8

Piper retrofractum Rosita (F2) #14479, RT=21.873 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 340.1902@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	NP-001798	20.23	C16 H17 N O2	255.12572	5.93e7

Piper retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13344, RT=20.249 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 256.1330@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	NP-004713	14.63	C15 H24 O2	236.17732	1.10e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #9568, RT=14.644 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 237.1846@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	NP-006206	20.67	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N O ₃	259.12053	1.31e9

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13626, RT=20.661 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 260.1278@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	NP-016141	21.98	C22 H29 N O3	355.21430	1.33e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14544, RT=21.970 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 356.2215@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	NP-016582	22.72	C ₂₀ H ₃₅ N O	305.27159	3.03e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15048, RT=22.723 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 306.2787@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	NP-017152	15.50	C13 H23 N O2	225.17249	8.16e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10145, RT=15.502 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C13 H23 N O2 as [M+H]⁺1

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10150, RT=15.510 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 226.1798@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	NP-019401	9.46	C11 H15 N O2	193.10999	9.53e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #6105, RT=9.451 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 194.1173@ (30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	NP-020240	18.02	C14 H20 O3	236.14097	5.69e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11830, RT=18.026 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 237.1845@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	N''-(1H-1,2,4-Triazol-5-ylcarbonyl)carbonohydrionic diamide	4.66	C4 H7 N7 O	169.07118	8.97e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #2996, RT=4.670 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 170.0785@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	O-Ethyl (2-cyanopropan-2-yl)phenylphosphinothioate	16.16	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N O P S	253.06922	8.43e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10965, RT=16.732 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 254.1149@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	O-Methylauricine	21.78	C ₃₉ H ₄₆ N ₂ O ₆	638.33464	4.85e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14415, RT=21.782 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 639.3419@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Ochramide B	12.75	C ₁₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	238.16784	3.75e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #8292, RT=12.748 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 239.1751@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Octyl 1H-indole-1-carbodithioate	21.27	C17 H23 N S2	305.12590	1.10e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13935, RT=21.101 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 306.2786@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Oleamide	22.89	C ₁₈ H ₃₅ N O	281.27164	6.04e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15184, RT=22.923 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 282.2787@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	oleylanilide	22.84	C ₂₄ H ₃₉ N O	357.30266	1.41e7

Piper retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15124, RT=22.836 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 358.3099@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Orthophosphate	1.76	H3 O4 P	97.97674	8.90e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1130, RT=1.762 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 98.9840@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Oxaloterpin E	22.09	C ₂₁ H ₃₃ N O ₂	331.25066	1.16e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14624, RT=22.090 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 332.2943@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	oxazolone	2.02	C3 H3 N O2	85.01614	1.23e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1308, RT=2.035 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 86.0962@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Oxprenolol	18.77	C ₁₅ H ₂₃ N O ₃	265.16742	4.17e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12313, RT=18.751 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 266.1747@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	P-Phenylphosphonothioic dihydrazide	2.04	C6 H11 N4 P S	202.04502	1.86e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1316, RT=2.046 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 203.0522@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Paecilopeptin	7.61	C13 H24 N2 O3	256.17833	7.27e6

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Paenibacillin A	4.20	C11 H18 N2 O	194.14154	4.61e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #2710, RT=4.227 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 195.1223@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Papupyrrolal	20.02	C15 H17 N O3	259.12042	1.01e8

Piper retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13161, RT=19.982 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 260.1277@(30:50:80), +1)

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Penicillenol D1	18.60	C16 H23 N O3	277.16745	9.84e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12204, RT=18.589 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 278.1747@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Penicillic acid	7.34	C8 H10 O4	170.05769	5.42e6

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Penipaline C	21.37	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N O ₂	229.10986	1.87e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14125, RT=21.373 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 230.1171@(30:50:80), +1)

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	PGE2alpha dimethyl amine	22.34	C22 H41 N O3	367.30815	8.94e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14793, RT=22.344 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 368.2215@(30:50:80), +1)

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Phenethyl 5-oxo-L-prolinate	13.92	C13 H15 N O3	233.10484	1.45e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #9081, RT=13.919 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 234.1121@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Phomopsisin A	20.77	C ₂₂ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₅	404.23057	2.20e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13707, RT=20.776 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 405.2379@(30;50;80), +1)

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Phormidinine B	21.78	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ N O ₂	301.20361	1.21e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14434, RT=21.808 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 302.1382@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Piperanine	21.47	C17 H21 N O3	287.15175	9.67e9

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Piperidine	2.73	C5 H11 N	85.08898	9.31e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1746, RT=2.722 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 86.0963@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Piperine	22.09	C17 H19 N O3	285.13609	1.44e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14634, RT=22.106 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 286.1434@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	pipoxizine	21.69	C ₂₄ H ₃₁ N O ₃	381.22978	4.29e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14350, RT=21.691 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 382.2370@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Plumbagin	18.48	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₃	188.04708	2.61e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12160, RT=18.521 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 189.1635@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Polygodial	21.14	C15 H22 O2	234.16159	4.35e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13960, RT=21.136 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 235.1688@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Porphobilinogen	13.44	C10 H14 N2 O4	226.09499	3.52e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #8721, RT=13.384 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 227.1750@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Pregnenolone 16alpha-carbonitrile	22.37	C22 H31 N O2	341.23487	4.19e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14815, RT=22.376 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 342.2059@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Preussin B	22.68	C ₁₉ H ₃₁ N O	289.24019	5.59e8

Piper retrofractum Rosita (F2) #15036, RT=22.705 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 290.2475@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Preussin H	22.24	C ₂₁ H ₃₅ N O ₂	333.26623	2.75e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14764, RT=22.300 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 334.2736@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Proline	4.07	C5 H9 N O2	115.06310	5.01e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #2622, RT=4.092 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 116.0704@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Propafenone	22.07	C ₂₁ H ₂₇ N O ₃	341.19847	5.84e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14616, RT=22.080 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 342.2057@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Propranolol	18.92	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N O ₂	259.15681	2.73e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #12438, RT=18.938 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 260.1641@(30;50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Propylnorapomorphine	12.02	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N O ₂	295.15682	7.47e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #7788, RT=12.002 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 296.1641@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Prototenellin C	21.18	C22 H27 N O6	401.18321	1.42e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13995, RT=21.188 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 402.2268@ (30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Radianspene L	21.79	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ N O ₃	327.18296	1.10e9

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14431, RT=21.805 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 328.1902@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Smenospongimine	22.07	C22 H31 N O3	357.22972	1.46e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14606, RT=22.064 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 358.2372@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	SMTP-6	21.98	C34 H40 N2 O6	572.28832	1.11e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14546, RT=21.972 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 573.2972@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	sn-glycero-3-Phosphocholine	1.86	C8 H20 N O6 P	257.10242	1.89e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1179, RT=1.838 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 258.1097@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	sn-glycero-3-Phosphoethanolamine	1.79	C5 H14 N O6 P	215.05551	3.91e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1145, RT=1.784 min, MS1, FTMS (+)
C5 H14 N O6 P as [M+H]⁺

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #1150, RT=1.792 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 216.0628@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Solanapyrone N	20.02	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ N O ₄	317.16221	5.74e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13287, RT=20.163 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 318.1332@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Stachybotrin A	21.21	C ₂₃ H ₃₁ N O ₅	401.21945	8.32e7

Piper retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14002, RT=21.197 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 402.1905@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Stachlyline A	12.22	C13 H17 N O3	235.12050	2.46e7

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Streptimidone	20.77	C16 H23 N O4	293.16232	2.09e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13701, RT=20.767 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 294.1695@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Streptophenazine H	16.66	C ₂₄ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₆	440.19411	1.62e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10928, RT=16.677 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 441.2014@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	SW-B	21.81	C13 H23 N O	209.17768	1.02e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14426, RT=21.798 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 210.1849@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Terbutaline	12.97	C12 H19 N O3	225.13615	1.40e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #8440, RT=12.967 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 226.1434@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	tert-butyl 4-(3-aminopropyl)piperazine-1-carboxylate	4.63	C12 H25 N3 O2	243.19424	7.29e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #2973, RT=4.634 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 244.2015@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	tert-Butyl [2-(2-aminoethoxy)ethyl]carbamate	7.33	C9 H20 N2 O3	204.14694	2.12e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #4712, RT=7.320 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 205.0241@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	tert-Butyl hydrazodiformate	8.71	C ₁₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄	232.14199	9.36e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #5604, RT=8.688 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 233.1493@ (30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Tetrahydropalmatine	21.63	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ N O ₄	355.17793	6.46e7

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Tetramethylene glutarimide	13.94	C9 H13 N O2	167.09438	2.69e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #9075, RT=13.910 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 168.1017@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Thebaine	21.74	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N O ₃	311.15166	8.89e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14366, RT=21.714 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 312.1588@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Toliprolol	16.55	C ₁₃ H ₂₁ N O ₂	223.15691	3.69e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10854, RT=16.567 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 224.1643@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Tolterodine	22.52	C ₂₂ H ₃₁ N O	325.24017	3.43e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14901, RT=22.503 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 326.2473@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Trans-1-hydroxy-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4-isobutylpyrrolidine-2,5-dione	15.32	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N O ₄	263.11539	2.38e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #10038, RT=15.345 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 264.1226@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Trofinetide	20.76	C13 H21 N3 O6	315.14424	9.55e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13705, RT=20.774 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 316.1515@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Tropine	9.92	C8 H15 N O	141.11514	1.95e7

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Type IV cyanolipid 16:0 ester	22.60	C ₂₁ H ₃₇ N O ₂	335.28202	1.89e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14962, RT=22.592 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 336.2892@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Type IV cyanolipid 20:1(11Z) ester	22.80	C ₂₅ H ₄₃ N O ₂	389.32891	1.22e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15115, RT=22.823 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 390.3361@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Type IV cyanolipid 20:2 ester	22.76	C ₂₅ H ₄₁ N O ₂	387.31331	7.94e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15084, RT=22.777 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 388.3206@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Vanillin	9.46	C8 H8 O3	152.04714	2.09e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #6118, RT=9.470 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 153.0544@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Vindoline	21.27	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₆	456.22530	4.36e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14049, RT=21.265 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 457.2325@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Xenocloin E	21.65	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ N O ₃	301.16722	6.20e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14331, RT=21.665 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 302.1745@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Xestospongins C	21.95	C ₂₈ H ₅₀ N ₂ O ₂	446.38651	4.51e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14532, RT=21.952 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 447.3940@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	Zinnimidine	17.22	C15 H19 N O3	261.13612	5.41e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11304, RT=17.237 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 262.1434@(30:50:80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	{(4a <i>S</i> ,6a <i>S</i> ,6b <i>R</i> ,8a <i>R</i> ,13a <i>R</i> ,13b <i>R</i> ,15b <i>S</i>)-4a-[(Benzyloxy)carbonyl]-2,2,6a,6b,9,9,13a-heptamethyl-1,2,3,4,4a,5,6,6a,6b,7,8,8a,9,13,13a,13b,14,15b-octadecahydro-11H-chryseno[1,2- <i>f</i>]indazol-11-yl}acetic acid	22.83	C ₄₀ H ₅₄ N ₂ O ₄	626.40752	2.11e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15140, RT=22.860 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 627.4146@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	{(4a <i>S</i> ,6a <i>S</i> ,6b <i>R</i> ,8a <i>R</i> ,13a <i>R</i> ,13b <i>R</i> ,15b <i>S</i>)-4a-[(Benzyloxy)carbonyl]-2,2,6a,6b,9,9,13a-heptamethyl-1,2,3,4,4a,5,6,6a,6b,7,8,8a,9,13,13a,13b,14,15b-octadecahydro-11H-chryseno[1,2- <i>f</i>]indazol-11-yl}acetic acid	22.55	C ₄₀ H ₅₄ N ₂ O ₄	626.40752	3.62e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #14920, RT=22.530 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 627.3420@(30;50;80), +1)

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	{3-[(E)-2-(1,3-Benzodioxol-5-yl)vinyl]-2-oxiranyl}(1-piperidiny)methanone	17.13	C17 H19 N O4	301.13103	6.30e8

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11232, RT=17.135 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 302.1383@(30;50;80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	{4-Ethyl-2-[(9Z)-9-octadecen-1-yl]-4,5-dihydro-1,3-oxazol-4-yl}methanol	22.65	C ₂₄ H ₄₅ N O ₂	379.34432	6.56e6

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #15015, RT=22.671 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 380.3153@(30;50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	α-Linolenoyl ethanolamide	18.05	C20 H35 N O2	321.26635	9.76e7

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #11850, RT=18.058 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 322.2737@(30:50:80), +1)

Compounds

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File name: Piper retrofractum

Study: Rosita_Handayani_UNAIR

Structure	Name	RT [min]	Formula	Calc. MW	Areas
	α -Pyrrolidinobutyphenone	21.15	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ N O	217.14632	2.21e9

Piper_retrofractum_Rosita (F2) #13998, RT=21.194 min, MS2, FTMS (+), (HCD, DDA, 218.1536@(30:50:80), +1)

